

Technical efficiency and production risk in Scottish Agriculture: Impacts on the livestock & arable sectors

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Executive Summary

Technical efficiency and production risk are both important measures of farm performance. Technical efficiency identifies which farms do more with less, while production risk identifies uncertainty and variability in farm outputs and can be considered a key aspect of farm resilience.

Using the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data from 2003–2022 we calculate farm technical efficiency while accounting for production risk. This enables us to identify the prevalence of production inefficiency and production risk, which is related to farms' resilience capacity. We also explore factors associated with higher technical efficiency and lower production risk. While some interventions might contribute to improving technical efficiency and reducing production risk e.g. crop diversification, others might better address technical efficiency e.g. land reform to support long-term investment, or production risk e.g. crop insurance. By considering these performance indicators together we can better diagnose the challenges facing farms in Scotland.

The main finding is that farm performance in Scottish agriculture has been highly volatile and there are few common drivers of farm performance across different farm types. Production risk is highly prevalent in livestock farming systems while technical inefficiency is pronounced in arable farms. This means that policy intervention should focus more on ensuring business stability and resilience in the livestock farming sector and reducing production in-efficiency in the arable farming sector.

One key factor that stands out in determining farm performance is the share of subsidy to total farm income. Farms where the share of subsidy to total farm income is high tend to be more technically inefficient; however, they also tend to have lower levels of production risk. Policymakers should ensure that new subsidy regimes implemented under the Agricultural Reform Bill continue to support farms by helping to mitigate against production risk while not holding back potential efficiency gains.

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Based on this, different emphases on the role of subsidy should be devised: such as increasing the conditionality of subsidies.

- 1. Conditional Subsidies:** Link subsidy payments to specific performance metrics or sustainable farming practices, incentivizing farmers to adopt more efficient and environmentally friendly methods.
- 2. Subsidy Diversification:** Explore alternative subsidy mechanisms, such as insurance schemes, price stabilization funds, or investment support, to address various aspects of risk and efficiency more holistically.
- 3. Efficiency-based Farmer Education and Extension:** Invest in farmer training and advisory services to help them optimize their operations across different levels of efficiency and leverage subsidies more effectively, reducing their reliance on subsidies in the long run.

Enhancing farmers' participation in cooperatives and the use of digital technologies for agricultural activities can be also considered as ways of improving farm performance.

Detailed research briefs are available separately for the arable and livestock farming sectors, providing comprehensive insights into methodological approaches and results.

SRUC-B3-1 Ensuring positive behavioural change for farmers towards best practice for clean growth

Research brief two

**Technical efficiency and production risk in Scottish Agriculture:
Impacts on the arable farming sector**

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Summary

Improving the efficiency and productivity of the agriculture sector is at the heart of supporting sustainable food supply stipulated in the Scottish government's agricultural reform route map. Arable farming in Scotland accounts for a third of agricultural production. However, there is a substantial degree of production uncertainty related to, for example, adverse weather conditions and the outbreak of pests and weeds. Thus, farmers' risk perceptions influence their input use decisions with potentially serious implications on production risk and technical efficiency. Understanding the key drivers of technical efficiency and production risk is essential to identify farm-specific measures necessary to achieve sustainable agricultural productivity change. Particularly, whether subsidies affect technical efficiency, production risk or both deserves special attention. Technical efficiency indicates the rate at which physical inputs are converted into physical outputs. Measuring technical efficiency entails defining a frontier, which represents the maximum potential output a given farm could produce with a given set of inputs. In other words, the frontier is a benchmark against which the actual level of production will be compared. On the other hand, production risk is defined as risks arising from uncertain natural growth processes, such as weather, pests, weeds and disease, which cause variations in expected yield.

We utilized data from the Farm Business Survey (FBS) covering the period 2003–2022 to analyse the efficiency of specialist cereals and general cropping arable farms. Our efficiency measure accounts for production risk. Incorporating production risk allows us to accurately estimate the sources of variations in production from its frontier level. We find that accounting for production risk reduces the technical efficiency of specialist cereal farms with no clear effect on general cropping farms.

While technical efficiency has been highly volatile over the past two decades, arable farms are still operating below their full potential implying the need for farm-specific interventions to increase farm performance. Farm subsidies, the 2015 CAP reform and agricultural output price change negatively and significantly reduce efficiency across all farm types; however, they serve as an effective risk management tool. Moreover, the use of digital technologies like the internet and expenditure on various software improve efficiency.

Generally, arable farming is less efficient as it only reaches 60% of its potential production capacity. This could be achieved by promoting widespread adoption of digital technologies, encouraging farmers' participation in various farming cooperatives' and facilitating specialized agricultural training.

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1. Introduction

Improving the efficiency of production systems is fundamental to achieving sustainable agricultural transition, which is at the centre of Scotland's post-Brexit framework for the support of farmers. How farmers perceive risk will affect, amongst others, voluntary uptake of measures and overall investment decisions which would influence the outcomes of the new payment scheme. A previous study found that risk attitude varies. The majority of farmers were classified as risk averse, while around a quarter of studied farmers were evaluated as risk takers (Barnes et al., 2021).

It is unequivocally agreed that arable farming is a risky business as farmers make input-use decisions without knowing the true state of nature (yield effect). Due in part to the length of the natural growth process, which involves various natural and manmade activities, the production system is also highly vulnerable to the variability of actual output from its expected level. For instance, bad weather conditions and the outbreak of pests and weeds make the production system highly uncertain. This implies that input allocation decisions are made based on farmers' subjective probability of taking some level of risk. Higher use of inputs in agricultural production is considered a viable strategy to increase agricultural yield, assuming inputs have a similar effect on total output and variability (production risk). However, this is not always the case. Some inputs may increase output at the expense of higher risk, while others may reduce risk and increase output. This means that farmers' input use decisions aim at maximising output and minimising production risk. Despite farmers' input allocation decisions having serious implications on both production risk and technical inefficiency, the focus so far has been only on the latter, neglecting production risk as a source of output variation from its frontier. Therefore, farm performance measures using technical efficiency scores should account for the role of production risk to better understand the interplay between input use decisions, production risk and technical inefficiency.

A production risk-adjusted technical efficiency estimate measures farmers' capacity to produce the maximum attainable level of output using existing inputs or producing an existing output using less amount of input after accounting for the contribution of production risk. It also allows us to understand the implications of farmers' input use decisions on production risk and output change in a single modelling framework.

Hence, the overarching goal of this brief is to measure the performance of the arable farming sector over the last two decades using a production risk-adjusted technical efficiency as a farm performance metric in Scotland. Understanding the underlying factors behind the variation in technical inefficiency and production risk is also the other objective we address in this brief. Through this, we advance farm performance evaluations conducted before (see Barnes et al. 2022 which did not accommodate risk) and provide fresh evidence on the effect of various factors on risk-adjusted technical inefficiency and production risk among arable farms in Scotland.

2. Method

The Farm Business Survey (FBS) collects detailed financial and production-related data for a set of farms in Scotland. The depth of the survey offers an understanding of the financial performance

of farms over time. The sample ranges between 400 and 510 farms per year across the 2003–2022 timeframe. Using this panel, we employ Kumbhakar’s (2002) approach, which extends the Just and Pope (1978) method of accounting for production risk to accommodate technical inefficiency and production risk in a single model.

Our modelling framework entails estimating a single random effect flexible production function in the stochastic frontier analysis framework which incorporates three components: average output, technical inefficiency component and the production risk component.

3. Results

3.1. Risk-adjusted Efficiency

We present the trend of technical efficiency with and without accounting for production risk for general cropping and specialist cereals farming systems over the last two decades in the upper and lower panels of Figure 1, respectively.

Figure 1: Trend of arable farming TE with and without accounting for production risk.

Overall, the results reveal that farmers' performance in the arable farming sector has been highly volatile. Accounting for production risk substantially changes specialist cereal farms' technical efficiency alone. Unlike the general cropping farms, where accounting for production risk does not change the trend of technical efficiency, accounting for production risk reduces the level of technical efficiency for specialist cereal farms across all years. This means that for specialist cereal

farms, failure to account for production risk in technical efficiency measurement would erroneously, overestimate their performance, which will have misleading policy implications. It is important to jointly model production risk and technical efficiency since the interventions to deal with production risk may not necessarily improve efficiency. It is also evident that arable farming in Scotland is still operating below its full potential and actions are needed to reduce inefficiency while managing production risk.

3.2. Contribution to Production Risk

Figure 2 presents the varying effects of inputs on average output and production risk for general cropping (upper panel) and specialist cereal (lower panel) farms. The coefficients map the magnitude of the impact and the error bars the 95 % confidence intervals. If they cross the red dashed line, coefficients are not significantly different from zero. The results show that the effect of inputs on production risk and output varies depending on the farm type.

For both farm types, intermediate inputs improve output while serving as an effective risk management tool. Intermediate inputs, which constitute expenditure on crop protection, seed, electricity and energy, fertilizer and other miscellaneous expenses, are expected to provide output-enhancing as well as risk-reducing benefits. On one hand, they serve as an immediate agricultural input required for crop production; on the other hand, they minimize production uncertainty due to pest infestations, crop diseases, and weeds.

Figure 2: The effect of inputs on output and production risk of arable farming

Moreover, capital and land have a mixed effect. While capital increases output and production risk for general cropping farms, it only significantly reduces the risk for specialist cereals with negligible effects on output. Utilizing large and advanced agricultural equipment in agriculture is expected to minimize output variability by facilitating the timely collection of harvest before adverse weather conditions and crop diseases destroy it. Land significantly increases output for both farm types

but also exacerbates production risk for specialist cereal farms. This could be due to constraints on applying effective risk management activities when farmers manage a large land size.

3.2. Determinants of inefficiency and production risk.

Agricultural policies and interventions aimed at improving production efficiency and ensuring business stability in the agriculture sector require prior information about what drives variation in production risk and technical inefficiency across farming systems. To this end, we present the determinants of technical inefficiency and production risk in panel A and panel B of Table 1, respectively. While we accounted for a host of factors in our estimation, we emphasize here on statistically significant results alone. Positive signs indicate the factor has a significant effect that increases technical inefficiency and production risk. Negative signs indicate the factor has a significant effect that decreases technical inefficiency and production risk.

Overall, we find that change in inefficiency and production risk is associated with different factors across the two farming systems. Focusing on consistent factors, using computers for business recording purposes, type of land tenure, the share of subsidies in total agricultural income, and market and policy changes significantly influence the technical inefficiency of arable farming.

Relative to owner-occupied lands, tenanted lands attain a higher efficiency level while mixed tenant increases inefficiency. Even if landowners are expected to engage in sustainable land management investment activities, tenants may also bear important complementary inputs that would enhance efficiency, such as specialised agricultural knowledge, skills, and finance. Using computers for business recording purposes exacerbates inefficiency for both farm types. However, using the Internet for business activities and investing in various software to aid agricultural activity improves the efficiency of general cropping and specialist cereal farms, respectively. On the other hand, market shocks in the form of agricultural output price changes, and policy changes implemented in 2015, reduce the efficiency of both farming systems. Compared to the post-2015 period, efficiency is higher between 2003 and 2014, presumably due to the addition of stringent environmental regulations in 2015. 2015 brought the enhancement of cross-compliance measures, to better support environmental goals.

Share of subsidies from total agricultural income also significantly reduces the efficiency of arable farms. The income effect of the subsidies is expected to reduce the quality of on-farm labour supply (working motivation), input-output allocation decisions and investment in improved agricultural technologies. A similar effect of subsidies has been observed in the arable farming sector of Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands and France (Zhu and Lansink, 2010; Latruffe and Desjeux, 2016).

Unlike their effect on efficiency, subsidies consistently reduce production risk across the two arable farming systems. Subsidy income could serve as insurance against unexpected weather or pest-related crop damages. These results suggest that the net effects of subsidies on farm performance depend on whether their risk mitigation benefits outweigh their negative impact on technical efficiency. In line with our expectations, production risk is more prevalent in LFA farms and farms without successors.

Table 1: Determinants of technical inefficiency and production risk by farm type.

	Specialist cereals	General cropping
Technical inefficiency determinants (A)		
Subsidy share	+	+
Agri. Educ.		-
Family lab.		-
Tenanted	-	-
Mixed tenant	+	+
Share of environ. area	+	
Software	-	
Internet		-
Cooperative	-	
PC record	+	+
LFA	-	
Successor	+	
Market shock	+	+
Policy shock (2003–2014) [§]	+	+
Determinants of production risk (B)		
Subsidy share	-	-
Age		-
Education		+
LFA	+	
Successor		-
Market shock	-	
Policy shock (2003–2014) [§]	-	
Number of farms	1, 552	1, 059

[§] compared to 2015–2022

4. Summary

- A risk-adjusted technical efficiency measures the level of the technical efficiency score after accounting for output variability due to production risk. Production risk is the variability of total output from the frontier, which may stem from factors such as unfavourable weather conditions, pest infestations, and the outbreak of crop disease.
- Accounting for production risk in technical efficiency estimation reduces the technical efficiency of specialist cereal farms with no clear effect on general cropping farms.
- Agricultural input use decisions have different effects on crop output and production risk. For instance, intermediate inputs improve crop output while reducing production risk. However, for general cropping farms, an increase in output from capital is also associated with an increasing level of production risk.
- Subsidies decrease technical efficiency while the use of digital technologies like the internet and increased investment in software enhance efficiency.

- Production risk is mitigated by the share of subsidies over total agricultural income and having a successor.

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